

TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT FLEXURAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: We have proposed the accelerated testing method to predict the fatigue life of FRP under an arbitrary combination of frequency, temperature, and stress ratio based on the time-temperature superposition principle and discussed experimentally about the validity and applicability of our proposed method. It has been clarified from these studies that our proposed method is applicable to predict the tensile and flexural fatigue lives for unidirectional CFRP using PAN-based carbon fiber and epoxy resin. In this paper, the time-temperature dependence of flexural fatigue behavior of CFRP quasi-isotropic laminates using PAN-based carbon fiber and epoxy resin was evaluated experimentally, and the validity of our proposed method was confirmed for this CFRP laminates.

KEY WORDS: CFRP, Fatigue, Creep, Strength, Time-Temperature Dependence, Life Prediction

INTRODUCTION

The stress-strain relation of polymer resin exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of polymer composites also depends on time and temperature even below T_g which is within the normal operating-temperature range. These examples are shown by Aboudi et al. [1], Enyama et al. [2], Gates [3], McMurray et al. [4], Miyano et al. [5-7], and Sullivan [13].

For the development of FRP structures, therefore, a large amount of material properties data such as long-term fatigue and creep properties data as well as static strength data under various temperature conditions are needed for all of FRPs which are considered as candidates of structural materials. However, it is almost impossible to carry out time-consuming fatigue and creep tests under various temperature conditions as well as various loading conditions for all of these FRPs.

In our previous paper [8], we have proposed the accelerated testing methodology to predict the fatigue life of FRP under an arbitrary combination of frequency, temperature, and stress ratio based on the time-temperature superposition principle and discussed experimentally about the validity and applicability of our proposed method [9-12]. It has been clarified from these studies that our proposed method is applicable to predict the tensile and flexural fatigue lives for unidirectional CFRP using PAN-based carbon fiber and epoxy resin. In this paper, the time-temperature dependence of flexural fatigue behavior of CFRP quasi-isotropic laminates using PAN-based carbon fiber and epoxy resin is evaluated experimentally, and the applicability of our proposed method is discussed for this CFRP laminates.

PREDICTION PROCEDURE OF FATIGUE STRENGTH

The prediction method [8] rests on the four hypotheses, (A) same failure mechanism under constant strain-rate (CSR), creep, and fatigue loadings, (B) same time-temperature superposition principle for all failure strengths, (C) linear cumulative damage law for monotonic non-decreasing loading, and (D) linear dependence of fatigue strength upon stress ratio.

When these hypotheses are met, the fatigue strength under an arbitrary combination of frequency, stress ratio, and temperature can be determined based on the following test results: (a) master curve of CSR strength and (b) master curve of fatigue strength for zero stress ratio. The master curve of CSR strength is constructed from the test results at various constant strain-rates and temperatures. On the other hand, the master curve of fatigue strength at zero stress ratio can be constructed from the test results at single frequency for various temperatures based on the hypothesis (B).

The outline of this method is shown schematically in Fig.1 together with definitions of some notations. The detail of the method will be presented with experimental data.

- T, T_0 : temperature, reference temperature
- f, f' : frequency, reduced frequency
- t_s, t_c, t_f : time to failure under CSR(Constant Strain Rate), creep and fatigue loadings
- t'_s, t'_c, t'_f : reduced time to failure
- $a_{T0}(T)$: time-temperature shift factor ($a_{T0}(T)=t_s/t'_s=t_c/t'_c=t_f/t'_f=f'/f$)
- R : load ratio ($R=\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$)
- N_f : number of cycles to failure ($N_f=f \cdot t_f$)
- $\sigma_s, \sigma_c, \sigma_f$: CSR, creep and fatigue failure loads
- $\sigma_{f:0}, \sigma_{f:1}$: σ_f for $R=0$ and $R=1$

Fig.1 Prediction procedure of fatigue strength of FRP

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

CFRP quasi-isotropic laminates were made from plain-woven carbon fiber UT500 and a matrix epoxy resin #135. The stacking sequence of this CFRP laminate, UT500/#135, is [(45,-45)/(0,90)]_s.

The three-point bending tests for CSR, creep and fatigue loadings were conducted using same geometry of specimen; length $l=70\text{mm}$, width $b=15\text{mm}$, and thickness $h=1.9\text{mm}$. The span is

$L=50\text{mm}$. The CSR tests were conducted at three loading-rates $V=0.02, 2, 200 \text{ mm/min}$ and six constant temperatures from $T=25^\circ\text{C}$ to 170°C using an Instron type testing machine with a temperature chamber. The creep tests were conducted at three constant temperatures $T=25, 110, \text{ and } 170^\circ\text{C}$ using creep testing machine with a temperature chamber. The fatigue tests were conducted under three constant temperatures $T=25, 110, \text{ and } 170^\circ\text{C}$ for two loading frequencies $f=2 \text{ and } 0.02\text{Hz}$, and a stress ratio (minimum stress/maximum stress) $R=0.05$ using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine with a temperature chamber. Additionally, the fatigue tests were also conducted at $R=0.5$ for three temperatures.

The flexural failure stress σ is calculated from applied maximum load P_{\max} by

$$\sigma = \frac{3P_{\max}L}{2bh^2}. \quad (1)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Master curve of CSR failure stress

The left side of Fig.2 shows the flexural CSR failure stress σ_s versus time to failure t_s at various constant temperatures T , where t_s is the time period from initial loading to P_{\max} . The master curve was constructed by shifting σ_s at constant temperatures other than reference temperature T_0 along the log scale of t_s so that they overlap on σ_s at the reference temperature or on each other to form a single smooth curve as shown in the right side of Fig.2. Since σ_s at various temperatures can be superimposed smoothly, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for σ_s .

Fig.2 Master curve of CSR failure stress

The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ is defined by

$$a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{t_s}{t_s'} \quad (2)$$

where, t_s' is the corresponding time at the reference temperature T_0 called the reduced time to failure. The shift factors for σ_s obtained experimentally in Fig.2 are plotted in open circles in Fig.3; the dotted lines are the shift factors for the storage modulus E' of this CFRP laminates. They agree well with

each other which indicates that the time and temperature dependence of CSR failure stress is controlled by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

All of these shift factors are quantitatively in good agreement with two Arrhenius' equations with different activation energies ΔH :

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

where G is the gas constant, $8.314 \cdot 10^{-3}$ [kJ/(K·mol)].

Fig.3 Time-temperature shift factor for CSR failure stress

Master curve of creep failure stress

A prediction method for creep failure stress σ_c from the master curve of CSR failure stress using the linear cumulative damage law was presented in our previous paper [8]. Let $t_s(\sigma)$ and $t_c(\sigma)$ be the CSR and creep failure time for the stress σ . Suppose that the material experiences a nondecreasing stress history $\sigma(t)$ for $0 < t < t^*$ where t^* is the failure time under this stress history. The linear cumulative damage law states

$$\int_0^{t^*} \frac{dt}{t_c[\sigma(t)]} = 1 \quad (4)$$

When $\sigma(t)$ is a constant stress σ_0 , the above formula yields to $t^* = t_c(\sigma_0)$.

The left side of Fig.4 shows the creep failure stress σ_c at three temperatures which are shifted using the shift factor for CSR failure stress to the data at $T_0 = 25^\circ\text{C}$ on the right side. In the right side, the dotted curve represents the master curve of creep strength calculated based on Eq.(4) using the master curve of CSR failure stress plotted in solid line. The agreement between the predicted curve and the creep test data is satisfactory; this indicates the validity of the linear cumulative damage law and a common shift factor.

Fig.4 Master curve of creep failure stress

Master curve of fatigue failure stress at zero stress ratio

We regard the fatigue failure stress σ_f either as a function of the number of cycles to failure N_f or of the time to failure $t_f = N_f/f$ for a combination of frequency f , stress ratio R , temperature T and denote it either $\sigma_f(N_f; f, R, T)$ or $\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T)$. Further, we consider the CSR failure stress $\sigma_s(t_f; T)$ the fatigue failure stress at $N_f=1/2$, $R=0$, and $t_f=1/(2f)$; this is motivated by closeness of the line connecting the origin and $(\pi, 1)$ and the curve $[1+\sin(t-\pi/2)]/2$ for $0 < t < \pi$. At this point, we introduce special symbols for fatigue failure stress at zero and unit stress ratios by $\sigma_{f,0}$ and $\sigma_{f,1}$ where the latter corresponds to creep failure stress.

To describe the master curve of $\sigma_{f,0}$, we need the reduced frequency f' in addition to the reduced time t_f' , each defined by

$$f' = f \cdot a_{T_0}(T) , \quad t_f' = \frac{t_f}{a_{T_0}(T)} = \frac{N_f}{f'} \quad (5)$$

We introduce two alternative expressions for the master curve for zero stress ratio: $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f'; f', T_0)$ and $\sigma_{f,0}(t_f'; N_f, T_0)$. In the latter expression, the explicit reference to frequency is suppressed in favor of N_f . Equation (5) enables one to construct the master curve from the tests at a single frequency for various temperatures.

Curves of the flexural fatigue failure stress $\sigma_{f,0}$ versus the number of cycles to failure N_f , $\sigma_{f,0}-N_f$ curves, for $f=2\text{Hz}$ are shown in Fig.5 where $\sigma_{f,0}$ at $N_f=1/2$ is represented by σ_s at $t_s=(2f)^{-1}$. In the upper figure of Fig.6, $\sigma_{f,0}$ versus the reduced time to failure t_f' curves for several reduced frequencies f' at the reference temperature T_0 are depicted by solid lines, which are obtained by converting N_f on Fig.5 into t_f' using Eq.(5) and the shift factor for CSR failure stress. The master curves of $\sigma_{f,0}$ for fixed N_f indicated by solid lines in the lower figure are constructed by connecting the points of the same N_f on the curves of each f' indicated by dotted lines in this figure.

In order to verify the master curves, we predicted the $\sigma_{f,0}-N_f$ curves at $f=0.02\text{Hz}$ and compared them with the test results as shown in Fig.7. Since the $\sigma_{f,0}-N_f$ curves predicted on the basis of the superposition principle agree well with the test results, we can conclude that the time-temperature superposition principle holds for fatigue failure stress. It also shows the validity of using the time-temperature shift factor for CSR failure stress for the construction of fatigue master curves.

Fig.5 Fatigue failure stress versus number of cycles to failure for frequency $f=2\text{Hz}$

Fig.6 Master curves of fatigue failure stress

Fig.7 Fatigue failure stress versus number of cycles to failure for frequency $f=0.02\text{Hz}$

Prediction of fatigue failure stress for arbitrary stress ratio

We have the master curve of creep failure stress $\sigma_c(t_c'; T_0)$ from which follows the creep failure stress at any temperature T . The creep failure stress, in turn, may be regarded as the fatigue failure stress $\sigma_{f:1}(t_f; f, T)$ at unit stress ratio $R=1$ and arbitrary frequency f with $t_c=t_f$. Further, the master curves of fatigue failure stress $\sigma_{f:0}(t_f', f', T_0)$ can be obtained from tests with a single frequency and various temperatures. The fatigue strength $\sigma_{f:0}(t_f; f, T)$ at zero stress ratio for any combination of t_f, f, T can be read off from Fig.6 after evaluating the corresponding reduced time t_f' and frequency f' by use of Eq.(5).

Implementing hypothesis (D), we propose a formula to estimate the fatigue strength $\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T)$ at an arbitrary combination of f, R, T by

$$\sigma_f(t_f; f, R, T) = \sigma_{f:1}(t_f; f, T)R + \sigma_{f:0}(t_f; f, T)(1 - R) \quad (6)$$

Figure 8 shows experimental data of σ_f - t_f for $f=2\text{Hz}$, $R=0.05, 0.5, 1.0$ and $T=25, 110, 170^\circ\text{C}$. The solid lines represent the least squares fit for $R=0.05$ in Fig.6 which we consider the curves for $R=0$, while the chain lines are the creep failure stress obtained in Fig.4. The dotted lines are calculated from Eq.(6) on the basis of the curves for $R=0$ and $R=1$, respectively. As can be seen, the predictions correspond well with the experimental data for all temperatures tested. Therefore, the validity of the hypothesis (D) for fatigue failure stress is confirmed.

Fig.8 Fatigue failure stress versus time to failure for three stress ratios

Failure mechanism under CSR, creep, and fatigue loadings

The flexural failure processes under CSR, creep, and fatigue loadings are very characteristic, respectively, before the final failure for all temperature conditions. In the CSR tests, firstly the delamination was observed, and then the transverse crack was observed as shown in the left hand side of Fig.9. In the creep tests, firstly the transverse crack was observed, and then the delamination was observed as shown in the center of Fig.9. In the fatigue tests, firstly the delamination was observed, and then the transverse crack was observed. These failures were propagated before the final failure as shown in the right hand side of Fig.9. However, all specimens failed suddenly when the 0 degree

layer on the compression side of the specimen failed after the above mentioned failure processes. From SEM photographs shown in Fig.10, the compressive fracture of 0 degree layer is triggered by the microbuckling of warp fibers. Therefore, the hypothesis (A); same failure mechanism under CSR, creep, and fatigue loadings; is limited to the final step of failure.

Fig.9 Flexural failure processes under CSR, creep, and fatigue loadings

T °C	CSR V=2mm/min	Creep R=1	Fatigue R=0.05 f=2Hz
25	 $t_s=4.19\text{min}$ $\sigma_s=746.8\text{MPa}$	 $t_c=71.3\text{min}$ $\sigma_c=542.2\text{MPa}$	 $N_f=13765$ $\sigma_f=395.8\text{MPa}$
110	 $t_s=3.70\text{min}$ $\sigma_s=563.3\text{MPa}$	 $t_c=115.4\text{min}$ $\sigma_c=405.5\text{MPa}$	 $N_f=21810$ $\sigma_f=354.9\text{MPa}$
170	 $t_s=2.56\text{min}$ $\sigma_s=269.4\text{MPa}$	 $t_c=134.7\text{min}$ $\sigma_c=134.7\text{MPa}$	 $N_f=1268$ $\sigma_f=156.8\text{MPa}$

Fig.10 Fracture appearances after CSR, creep, and fatigue tests

CONCLUSION

In our previous paper, we proposed the accelerated testing method to predict the fatigue life of FRP under an arbitrary combination of frequency, temperature, and stress ratio based on the time-temperature superposition principle. The time-temperature dependence of flexural fatigue behavior of CFRP quasi-isotropic laminates using PAN-based carbon fiber and epoxy resin was evaluated experimentally, and the validity of our proposed method was confirmed for this CFRP laminates.

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